

The molar conductance of these complexes in chloroform are found to be quite low (3.2-8.2) showing thereby the non-electrolytic nature of the complexes. This suggests that chlorine atoms are coordinated to the metal ion and are not present in the ionic form.

The bonds occurring at 1600, 1430 and 1060 cm^{-1} , in the IR spectra of the metal complexes were discussed by earlier workers¹⁻⁵ to decide the donor atoms of the substituted thiourea. The bands appearing at 1600 cm^{-1} was assigned to ($\text{C}=\text{C}+\text{C}=\text{N}$). Except in two cases this band remains almost constant and thus enables the ruling out of the possibility of metal ligand co-ordination through nitrogen or pyridine ring.

The sulphur of substituted thioureas has been found to be one of the co-ordination sites by various workers in this field¹⁻⁶. Yamaguchi et al⁴ were of the opinion that the band assigned to $\nu(\text{N}-\text{C}-\text{N}+\text{C}=\text{S})$ was more important in the diagnosis of metal-sulphur bond where as Swaminathan et al⁵ have given more importance to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{S})$ band. But the latter band occurs in the region where many other bands of thiourea are also found and hence its detection is associated with quite some difficulty. Banerji et al⁶ have observed that these bands show shifts to lower frequencies and/or reduce in intensity in the case of metal complexes of N-N' bis (pyridyl) thiourea. Similar observations (lowering of intensity) have been made in the present case too. Moreover, it is found that the intensity of bands is reduced to such an extent, in some of the cases, that the band either disappears completely or its detection is very difficult. In one case these bands are found to be shifted to even higher frequency with lower intensity. Generally on complexation the ligand stretching frequencies are shifted to lower regions due to a decrease in the band order and consequently the force constant. But in some cases, i.e. in nitrile complexes, the $\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$ stretching frequencies⁷ and in biuret-metal complexes the N-H stretching frequencies⁸ are found to be increased. This suggests the possibility of metal-ligand co-ordination through sulphur of thiocarbonyl group.

Differences in the position and intensity of metal sulphur bands $\nu(\text{C}=\text{S})$, $\nu(\text{N}-\text{C}-\text{N}+\text{C}=\text{S})$ in different substituted thiourea complexes may be due to *p*-halo substitution in the pyridyl ring. The electron donating ability of the *p*-halo substituents is in the order $\text{I} > \text{Br} > \text{Cl}$. The electron from the halo-substituents are donated to the pyridine ring, from where these are delocalized with the thiocarbonyl group. As the electron density in the ground level is increased lesser energy is required for excitation and hence the position of band is shifted to longer wavelengths. The intensity of the transition band, which is related to the probability of the transition is also increased for the same reason. The irregularity observed in present case

precludes unambiguous confirmation of his hypothesis.

On the basis of foregoing discussion it is clearly seen that the substituted thioureas studied form 1 : 2 complexes with PdCl_2 in which the thioureas are linked through sulphur to metal and the chlorine atoms remained attached to the metal.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to the authorities of B.I.T.S., Pilani for providing necessary laboratory facilities and one of them (RPB) is thankful to UGC for a Junior Research Fellowship.

References

1. A. DUTTA AHMED and P. K. MANDAL, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1967, 29, 2347.
2. D. BANERJEE and I. P. SINGH, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1968, 6, 34.
3. N. KRISHNASWAMI and H.D. BHARGAVA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1969, 7, 710.
4. A. YAMAGUCHI, R. B. PENLAND, S. MIZUSHIMA, T. J. LANE, C. CURRAN and J.V. QUAGLIANO; *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 80, 527.
5. K. SWAMINATHAN and H.M.N.H. IRWING, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1964, 26, 1291.
6. B. C. KASHYAP, S. K. BANERJI and A. D. TANEJA, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1974, 37, 612.
7. M. F. A. EL-SAYED and R. K. SHELINE, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1958, 6, 187.
8. B. KEDZIA, P. X. ARMENDAREZ and K. NAKAMOTO; *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1968, 30, 849.

Syntheses of Copper(II) Complexes with Some new Tridentate Dibasic Schiff Bases

A. SYAMAL*, K. S. KALE AND S. BANERJEE**

Department of Chemistry, Regional Engineering College,
Kurukshetra 132 119, Haryana

and
Department of Applied Sciences and Humanities, Kurukshetra
University, Kurukshetra 132 119, Haryana.

Manuscript received 1 February 1977, revised 28 July 1977
accepted 3 October 1977

TRIDENTATE dibasic Schiff bases are novel in the sense that they force the metal (II and III) ions to dimerise or polymerise and as a result metal complexes with unusual magnetic and structural properties are formed^{1,2}. There has been considerable interest on the syntheses and magnetic properties of copper (II) complexes of ONO donor tridentate dibasic Schiff bases derived from salicylaldehyde or substituted salicylaldehyde and orthoaminophenol³. In this preliminary communication we report the syntheses of several new copper (II) complexes with the ligands

* For Correspondence.

** Department of Chemistry, Institute of Chemistry,
Madam Cama Road,
Bombay-400032.

NOTES

(I) derived from salicylaldehyde, 5-chlorosalicylaldehyde, 5-bromosalicylaldehyde, 3-methoxysalicylaldehyde, 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde and orthoaminobenzylalcohol. This is the first report on the metal complexes of these new ligands and we intend to make a comprehensive study of coordination behaviour of these ligands with various metal ions.

I.R.=H, 5-chloro, 5-bromo, 3-methoxy, 5, 6-benzo.

General method of syntheses of the complexes :

A methanolic solution of the appropriate Schiff base (0.005 mole in 50 ml) was added slowly to a methanolic solution (30 ml) of copper (II) acetate monohydrate (0.005 mole) and the mixture was refluxed for 2 hr while stirring magnetically. The separated precipitates were suction filtered, washed with methanol and dried under vacuum at room temperature. The analytical data are presented in Table 1.

attributed to the antiferromagnetic exchange between the interacting Cu^{2+} ions⁴. The copper(II) complexes of comparable ligands viz. the Schiff bases derived from salicylaldehyde or substituted salicylaldehyde and orthoaminophenol exhibit low magnetic moments and are involved in antiferromagnetic exchange³.

The complexes exhibit a d-d band at 15400-17100 cm^{-1} (reflectance spectra, Table 1). The origin of a band at around 27000 cm^{-1} in these complexes is due to the symmetry forbidden ligand \rightarrow metal charge transfer transition rather than to the binuclear species^{5,6}. The infrared bands at 1600-1615 cm^{-1} can be attributed to the coordinated $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ stretch involving coordination through the nitrogen atom of the azomethine group since the free $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ stretch is known to appear at around 1640 cm^{-1} in aromatic Schiff bases^{7,8}.

The cryomagnetic and ESR studies of the complexes are in progress and details will be reported in due course.

Acknowledgement

The authors are indebted to the Department of Atomic Energy (Government of India) for financial support of this research.

TABLE—1 THE ANALYTICAL, INFRARED AND ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA OF COPPER(II) COMPLEXES^a

Complex	%Cu	%N	μ_{eff} B.M.	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ cm^{-1}	ν_{max} cm^{-1}
Cu(sal- <i>o</i> -aminobenzylalcohol)	Found : 21.8 Reqd. : 22.01	4.9 4.85	0.98	1610	17100
Cu(5-chlorosal- <i>o</i> -aminobenzylalcohol)	Found : 19.4 Reqd. : 19.66	4.1 4.33	1.39	1615	15400
Cu(5bromosal- <i>o</i> -aminobenzylalcohol)	Found : 17.0 Reqd. : 17.28	3.8 3.82	1.45	1615	16400
Cu(3methoxysal- <i>o</i> -aminobenzylalcohol)	Found : 19.9 Reqd. : 19.94	4.4 4.39	1.40	1600	not measured
Cu(hydrox- <i>o</i> -aminobenzylalcohol)	Found : 19.1 Reqd. : 18.75	4.1 4.14	1.31	1615	15400

^aAbbreviations : sal=salicylaldehyde, 5-chlorosal=5-chlorosalicylaldehyde, 5-bromosal=5-bromosalicylaldehyde, 3-methoxysal=3-methoxysalicylaldehyde and hydrox=2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde.

The infrared spectra of the complexes do not exhibit the νOH stretch and this is indicative of the deprotonation of the ligands and dibasic behaviour with oxygen coordination of the ligands. The complexes are insoluble in common solvents and melt or decompose at $>250^\circ$. This indicates dimeric or polymeric nature of the complexes. The magnetic susceptibilities of the complexes were measured by the Gouy method using $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_4]$ as the standard. The room temperature magnetic moments of the complexes are in the range 0.98-1.45 B.M. which is less than the spin-only value of 1.73 B.M. required for an $S = \frac{1}{2}$ system. The low magnetic moments are

References

1. D. J. HODGSON, Progress Inorganic Chemistry, 1975, 19, 1.
2. W. E. HATFIELD and R. WHYMAN, Transition Metal Chemistry, 1969, 5, 47.
3. A. P. GINSBERG, R. C. SHERWOOD and E. KOUBEK, J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem. 1967, 29, 353.
4. M. KATO, H. B. JONASSEN and J. C. FANNING, Chem. Rev., 1964, 64, 99.
5. L. DUBICKI and R. L. MARTIN, Inorg. Chem., 1966, 5, 2203.
6. A. K. GREGSON, R. L. MARTIN and S. MITRA, Proc. Roy. Soc. A, 1971, 320, 473.
7. H. H. FREEDMAN, J. Amer. Chem. Soc., 1961, 83, 2900.
8. L. E. DAVIDSON and V. E. HANNIGER, J. Amer. Chem. Soc., 1953, 75, 68.